

Supplementary material: Microbiome compositional data analysis for survival studies

Meritxell Pujolassos, Toni Susin and Malu Calle

Contents

1 Survival data description	1
2 coda_coxnet for survival data	2
3 Time assessment of coda_coxnet	6
References	8

This supplementary document of the manuscript “Microbiome compositional data analysis for survival studies” describes the analysis performed with `coda4microbiome::coda_coxnet()` function and includes a time-assessment analysis with different datasets.

1 Survival data description

We illustrate `coda_coxnet()` algorithm with microbiome data of Non-obese diabetic (NOD) mice from Zhang et al. (2018) study. The survival data was processed by Gu et al. (2023), who made it available as a phyloseq object. Metadata and microbiome data were downloaded from <https://github.com/wg99526/MiSurvGit/tree/main/Data>. We also provide the filtered data used for the present analysis as a text file available in DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10552383.

The **survival dataset** includes microbiome abundance of 348 OTU in 173 samples. Sample information also includes:

- **T1D** reports the development (or not) of Type 1 Diabetes (T1D): 0 for T1D free and 1 for T1D development.
- **T1DWeek** specifies the time at which T1D was diagnosed (i.e., survival time).
- **Sex** and **Antibiotics** are two variables that will be included as covariables in the analysis

```

load("biom.Rdata")
phy <- biom
phy
#> Loading required package: phyloseq
#> phyloseq-class experiment-level object
#> otu_table() OTU Table: [ 348 taxa and 173 samples ]
#> sample_data() Sample Data: [ 173 samples by 4 sample variables ]
#> tax_table() Taxonomy Table: [ 348 taxa by 7 taxonomic ranks ]
#> phy_tree() Phylogenetic Tree: [ 348 tips and 347 internal nodes ]

sample_data(phy)[1:10,]
#>      T1D T1Dweek Sex Antibiotics
#> JP105F7W 1      11  M      Tylosin
#> JP51F7W  1      20  M      Control
#> JP64F7W  1      24  F      Control
#> JP66F7W  0      30  F      Control
#> JP77F7W  1      24  M      Control
#> JP166F7W 0      30  F      Control
#> JP258F7W 0      30  M      Control
#> JP257F7W 0      30  M      Control
#> JP190F7W 0      30  M      Control
#> JP23F7W  1      16  F      Tylosin

```

Our analysis was performed at the genus level, keeping taxa present in at least 5% of samples:

```

phyg <- tax_glom(phy, taxrank = "Genus" )
phyg
#> phyloseq-class experiment-level object
#> otu_table() OTU Table: [ 36 taxa and 173 samples ]
#> sample_data() Sample Data: [ 173 samples by 4 sample variables ]
#> tax_table() Taxonomy Table: [ 36 taxa by 7 taxonomic ranks ]
#> phy_tree() Phylogenetic Tree: [ 36 tips and 35 internal nodes ]

phyg_f = filter_taxa(phyg, function(x) (sum(x == 0)/length(x)) <= 0.95, TRUE)
phyg_f
#> phyloseq-class experiment-level object
#> otu_table() OTU Table: [ 30 taxa and 173 samples ]
#> sample_data() Sample Data: [ 173 samples by 4 sample variables ]
#> tax_table() Taxonomy Table: [ 30 taxa by 7 taxonomic ranks ]
#> phy_tree() Phylogenetic Tree: [ 30 tips and 29 internal nodes ]

```

2 coda_coxnet for survival data

coda4microbiome for survival studies identifies the combination of taxa predictive for the development of a given event. We illustrate the application of the algorithm focusing on the association of microbiome and the risk of developing T1D in NOD mice.

We implement the analysis calling function `coda_coxnet()`:

```

library(coda4microbiome)

# Set data
x = data.frame(t(otu_table(phyg_f)))
time = as.numeric(sample_data(phyg_f)$T1Dweek)
status = as.numeric(sample_data(phyg_f)$T1D)
covars = data.frame(sample_data(phyg_f)$Sex, # Gender
                    sample_data(phyg_f)$Antibiotics) # Antibiotics

# Run coda4microbiome
set.seed(12345)
T1Dmodel <- coda_coxnet(x,
                        time,
                        status,
                        covar=covars,
                        lambda = "lambda.1se",
                        alpha = 0.9, nfolds = 5,
                        showPlots = FALSE,
                        coef_threshold = 0.01)

```

The first plot (Figure 1) shows cross-validation measures (C-index) at different lambda values. We can see that the default for lambda="lambda.1se" the algorithm selects 21 pairwise log-ratios that correspond to 21 different taxa (see below).

Figure 1: Cross-validation accuracy curve for different degrees of penalization.

The output of `coda_coxnet` provides the number, the name and the coefficients of the selected taxa:

```

T1Dmodel$taxa.num
#> [1] 4 5 7 9 12 13 14 15 17 18 19 21 22 23 24 25 26 27 28 29 30

T1Dmodel$taxa.name
#> [1] "X192342" "X2119418" "X681370" "X138389" "X214919" "X354574"
#> [7] "X4390755" "X259631" "X221429" "X177271" "X4469576" "X4407703"
#> [13] "X262095" "X4426641" "X1684221" "X376862" "X179547" "X170335"
#> [19] "X296045" "X259772" "X192222"

T1Dmodel$`log-contrast coefficients`

```

```

#> [1] 0.04048477 -0.07600130 -0.07460672 0.06639612 0.10273980 -0.06223160
#> [7] -0.09722632 -0.11528871 0.11426715 0.13390224 0.03916189 0.18959629
#> [13] -0.32365578 -0.01392624 -0.03133711 -0.04444689 -0.02413120 0.08122107
#> [19] 0.18465576 0.04440899 -0.14031405

```

The algorithm identified a microbial signature associated to the risk of developing T1D. The signature is defined by the relative abundances of two groups of taxa: taxa with a positive coefficient in the regression model, and taxa with a negative coefficient. This is represented in the **signature plot** (Figure 2), a bar plot that shows the selected taxa and their estimated regression coefficients.

```
T1Dmodel$`signature plot`
```


Figure 2: Microbial signature for T1D onset.

We summarized the individual risk of developing the event of interest as the *microbial risk score*. It is defined by the identified microbial signature and their respective abundances in each subject.

The **microbial risk score plot** (Figure 3) shows individual risk scores and the actual development of T1D for every sample:

Figure 3: Microbial risk score plot.

To evaluate the classification accuracy of the model, the algorithm returns different Harrell C-index measure: the apparent Harrell's C-index (the C-index of the signature applied to the same data that was used to generate the model) and the mean and sd of the cross-validation C-index (obtained from the output of `cv.glmnet()`):

```
T1Dmodel$`apparent Cindex`
#> [1] 0.6970652

T1Dmodel$`mean cv-Cindex`
#> [1] 0.539234

T1Dmodel$`sd cv-Cindex`
#> [1] 0.01447544
```

Finally, we can obtain the **survival curves** (Figure 4) stratifying samples based on their microbial risk score through `plot_survcurves()` function:

```
survcurve <- plot_survcurves(risk.score = T1Dmodel$risk.score,
                             time,
                             status,
                             strata.quantile = 0.5) # median of the microbial risk score
```


Figure 4: Survival curves stratified by microbial risk score.

3 Time assessment of coda_coxnet

We assessed time requirements of *coda4microbiome* algorithm using several survival datasets with varying sample and taxa sizes (Table 1). We simulated survival times of several datasets reported in Nearing et al. (2022) with a Weibull distribution.

Datasets used for this analysis are:

```
datasets = c("Office",
             "ArcticFreshwaters",
             "Ji_WTP_DS",
             "cdi_schubert",
             "hiv_noguerajulian",
             "ob_goodrich",
             "Blueberry" ,
             "sw_sed_detender")
```

The following script was used to simulate survival data:

```
for (i in datasets){

  # Load data
  path = paste("./", i, sep="")
  table = paste(i, "_genus_table.tsv", sep="")
  data = paste(i, "_metadata.tsv", sep="")

  # OTU Table
  genus_table <- read.csv(file.path(path, table), sep="\t", row.names = 1,
                          check.names = FALSE, comment.char="#")
  genus_table_filt <- data.frame(t(remove_rare_features(genus_table, 0.1)))
  otutab <- rownames_to_column(genus_table_filt, var = "id")

  # Sample Data
  metadata <- read.delim(file.path(path, data), row.names=1)
  samdat <- rownames_to_column(metadata, var = "id")

  dat <- inner_join (samdat, otutab, by = "id")
  dat <- column_to_rownames(dat, var = "id")

  rm(genus_table, genus_table_filt, otutab, metadata, samdat)

  # Arrange input data
  x <- dat[,-1]
  y <- as.factor(dat[,1])
  table(y)

  # Create time-to-event
  set.seed(1234567)

  indgrp1 = which(y == unique(y)[[1]])           # Get samples in group 1 only
  ngrp1 = length(indgrp1)                       # Number of samples in group 1

  Etime_grp1 = rweibull(ngrp1, 2, 5)           # Weibull Distribution of event times
  Etime_grp1[which(Etime_grp1 > 10)] = 10     # Times higher than 10 set to 10
```

```

indgrp2 = which(y == unique(y)[[2]])      # Get samples in group 2 only
ngrp2 = length(indgrp2)                  # Number of samples in group 2

Etime_grp2 = rweibull(ngrp2, 2, 10)      # Weibull Distribution of event times
Etime_grp2[which(Etime_grp2 > 10)] = 10  # Times higher than 10 set to 10

Event_time <- rep(0, length(y))          # Time to event
Event_time[indgrp1] <- Etime_grp1
Event_time[indgrp2] <- Etime_grp2

Event <- ifelse(y == unique(y)[[1]], 1, 0) # Event occurring (1) or not (0)

save.image(paste0("./Nearing_datasets_simsurv/",
                  i, "_simsurv", ".RData"))
}

```

Then we run `coda_coxnet()` function with all datasets, setting default parameters, and recorded the computational time for each of them:

```

start_time<- proc.time() #time control

for (i in datasets){

  fileDir = paste("./Nearing_datasets_simsurv/", i, sep="")
  fileName = paste(fileDir, "_simsurv.RData", sep="")
  load(fileName)
  cat(sprintf("%s \n", i));

  time = Event_time
  status = Event

  crohn_cox <- coda_coxnet(x,
                          time,
                          status,
                          covar = NULL,
                          lambda = "lambda.1se", nvar = NULL,
                          alpha = 0.9, nolds = 10, showPlots = TRUE,
                          coef_threshold = 0)

  present_time<- proc.time() #time control
  timeTot = present_time - start_time;
  cat(sprintf("%s , Time = %f \n", i, timeTot[[1]]));
  start_time = present_time;
}

```

To perform the analysis, we used a CPU Intel-Core i7-9700 computer with 3.0Ghz and 32Gb of RAM. Time requirements of the different datasets are reported in following table:

Table 1: Computation times of coda4microbiome for different datasets

Data Name	Observations	Variables	time (s)	time (min)
cdi_schubert	237	75	6.78	0.11
ob_goodrich	613	117	9.56	0.16
hiv_noguerajulian	170	140	15.53	0.26
Ji_WTP_DS	59	155	5.30	0.09
Office	625	242	47.41	0.79
ArcticFreshwaters	1023	274	76.20	1.27
Blueberry	63	418	42.13	0.70
sw_sed_detender	78	1025	1091.76	18.20

References

- Zhang, X.S., Li, J., Krautkramer, K.A., Badri, M., Battaglia, T., Borbet, T.C., et al. (2018) Antibiotic-induced acceleration of type 1 diabetes alters maturation of innate intestinal immunity. *ELife*. 7 e37816.
- Gu, W., Koh, H., Jang, H., Lee, B., and Kang, B. (2023) MiSurv: an Integrative Web Cloud Platform for User-Friendly Microbiome Data Analysis with Survival Responses. *Microbiology Spectrum*. 11 (3).
- Nearing, J.T., Douglas, G.M., Hayes, M.G. et al. (2022) Microbiome differential abundance methods produce different results across 38 datasets. *Nat Commun* 13, 342